

VocalHUM: real-time whisper-to-speech enhancement for patients with vocal frailty

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ABSTRACT

VocalHUM is a smart system aiming to enhance the intelligibility of patients' whispered speech in real-time, basing on real whispering, synthesized vowels, and consonant enhancement techniques. Its purpose is to facilitate the patient-caregiver communication, and it is primarily designed for patients in a temporary or prolonged state of physical and vocal frailty (e.g., respiratory infections, geriatric weakness, or partial/total paralysis). The development of the first prototype has been founded by the Innosuisse Swiss Innovation Agency, and this article focuses on evaluating the algorithmic component of the first realized prototype whose structured evaluation with patients in real contexts will start in the next months by the implementing partner. The work is structured as follows: Section 2 reports a summary of the state of the art regarding the characteristics of the whispered speech, Section 3 covers the technical implementation of the voice reconstruction algorithm, and Section 4 provides some insights about a perceptive test for preliminary validation and future works. A permanent link with audio recordings of a male speakers, with 3 examples in Italian, English and Spanish languages is provided¹. Indeed, preliminary tests have been done with the Italian language, but the implementation is promising for all non-tonal languages.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper focuses on the structure and development of the algorithmic components of VocalHUM, a smart system aiming to enhance the intelligibility of patients' whispered speech in real-time, basing on audio only.

VocalHUM aims to minimize the muscular and respiratory effort necessary to achieve adequate voice intelligibility and the physical movements required to speak at a normal intensity. It is primary designed for patients in a temporary or prolonged state of physical and vocal frailty (e.g., respiratory infections, geriatric weakness, or partial/total paralysis) with the ultimate purposes to facilitate the patient-caregiver communication and improve the use of speech-to-text tool and voice commands. However, VocalHUM focuses on speech characterized by correct articulation and proper linguistic production, in absence of speech disorders such as apraxia or dysarthria. Indeed, we consider unvoiced speech restoration and enhancement as a first necessary step to move forward the state of the art for what regards future solutions involving the linguistic

components of the speech. The VocalHUM System consists of a small and smart object (Figure 1) composed by:

- An electret microphone positioned on the cheek near the lips.
- A Single Board Computer: a tiny self-embedded headless computer.
- An inbuilt speaker used to reproduce the output.

The real-time enhancing algorithm (hereinafter cited as HUM) can be considered the "heart" of the VocalHUM technology and will run on the single board computer. Its structure and configuration have been fixed after a series of tests that considered different approaches. HUM is based on additive synthesis for synthesizing vowels, and enhancement techniques for modelling consonants. Summarizing, the presented work deepens the implementation path of VocalHUM, with the following structure. Section 2 reports a summary of the state of the art regarding the characteristics of the whispered speech, its differences with respect to normal speech, and related existing speech assistive technologies in clinical contexts. Section 3 covers the technical implementation of HUM, while the following ones are dedicated to results, future works, and discussion.

Figure 1: VocalHUM prototype.

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¹https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1zHRg5u_fRTtgLe65LXhAlw_WqEeb4PMI?usp=sharing

2. STATE OF THE ART

Speech intelligibility and reduced mobility are common issues in hospital settings and represent a central interesting topic for many other applicative fields too. However, there is still a lack of commercial products and marketed solutions implementing the state-of-the-art regarding real-time processing algorithms for speech enhancement and reconstruction. Due to this reason the state of the art is structured in different sections. The first is a fundamental overview to understand the involved acoustic features and behaviors regarding the whispered speech and its differences with the normally phonated speech. The second one is a summarized state of the art regarding the communication issues of patients in real contexts, while the third focuses on whisper-to-speech and enhancement prototypes, algorithms, and research. A last shortly introduces the added value of audio forensic techniques in facing speech reconstruction challenges. These topics are fundamental to contextualize both the challenges we had to face, and in particular the real-time necessary processing, the space and power supply potential of the apparatus, and the suitable technology to allow the prototype to be worn and used by end-users.

2.1 The whispered speech

HUM applies a whisper-to-speech transformation relying only on the audio streaming, without taking into account the linguistic component of the speech. This choice derives from the need to not burden the process not depending on phone models and annotated databases. A typical approach to speech enhancement exploits, for example, IPA annotations [22], [23], [29], but these annotated corpora are extremely rare for whispered speech and as far as we know not available for the Italian language. At the same time, it must be emphasized that whisper enhancement relying on the audio signal alone is a challenge not to be underestimated. For example, increasing the intensity of the signal is not enough to enhance intelligibility especially in real contexts, and it is rather necessary to reconstruct the missing or attenuated language-related segmental and supra-segmental components of the speech (such as pitch, loudness, sounds length and other factors influencing the rhythm and stress patterns of spoken language) [1], [9]. We refer here to a whispered speech belonging to the so-called soft whisper group [33]. We do not describe here the physiology of this speech modality, which can be delved into [15], [17], [35].

Its main acoustics characteristics derive from the lack of vocal fold vibrations which implies the absence of fundamental pitch (F0), and the derived harmonic relationships among formants (F1, F2, F3, F4) [13]. Then, respect to normal speech, the whispered speech presents several differences [10], [17], [27] such as:

- Almost total lack of F0 (and related features).

- Much flatter power-frequency distribution of formants between 500 and 2000 Hz.
- Formants' values tend to be higher in frequency.
- F1 usually shows the greater increase.
- F2 tends to be as powerful as F1.
- It normally 20 dB lower power than its phonated version.
- Longer lasting vowels.

Another crucial point is the perceptual aspect: whispered speech is commonly understood by the human auditory system in optimal conditions. Perceptive issues begin when the conditions are not exactly optimal, such as in presence of environmental noise. As underlined by [16], despite progress has been made in the development of speech enhancement algorithms focusing on speech quality, little progress has been made in improving speech intelligibility in critical conditions. Moreover, it should be noted that phone calls reduce the useful speech bandwidth with repercussions on voice quality, while a traditional audio signal amplifier in many cases it does not increase intelligibility, which depends on cross segmental and supra-segmental factors of speech [2]. Then, the identification and reconstruction of the acoustic features which vary between whisper and normal speech seems to be the first problems to be solved in order to improve the state of the art.

2.2 Speech assistive technologies in clinical contexts

The COVID-19 pandemic started in 2019 brought to light the already existing communication issues and isolation feelings in clinical contexts. These contexts are typically equipped (in the best of cases) of internal-phones or emergency bells, but nothing is adopted for what regards speech intelligibility enhancement or restoration. A sectorial investigation highlighted the presence of various patented methodologies and tools for speech enhancement, not strictly designed for the healthcare field; however, we're speaking of algorithms or circuits that are still limited to noise reduction, intensity gain, equalization, or echo cancellation², therefore not strictly focused on speech [3], [19]. Some industries sell speech enhancement tools, but these are only focused on tasks like noise removal and acoustic echo cancellation finalized to improve speech recognition, which is beyond our scope. Main examples are Cerence³, Alango⁴, and Advanced Bionics⁵.

More of the recent research attempts are focused on partially/totally larynxotomized patients, which are currently constrained to the use of invasive tools, laryngophones or throat microphones [5], [7], [11], [24], [25], [37]. When they learn to speak autonomously, they use the so-called esophageal speech, which is much more difficult to understand than whispered speech due to the partial or total lack

² Rakshit, S. K., Keen, M. G., Bostick, J. E., & Ganci Jr, J. M. (2020). U.S. Patent No. 10,529,355. Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office; Kates, J. M. (1984). U.S. Patent No. 4,454,609. Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office; Zhang, M., Cao, K., Zeng, X., & Sun, H. (2020). U.S. Patent No. 10,811,030.

Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office; Eisner, M., Huang, Z., & Duehren, D. (2015). U.S. Patent Application No. 14/561,026.

³ <https://www.cerence.com>

⁴ <http://www.alango.com>

⁵ <https://advancedbionics.com/it/it/home.html>

of vocal cords and the different phonation modality. To the best of authors' knowledge, the available solutions for this target are yet not acceptable to reach a large-scale success among patients; hardware devices are still limited to old-styled tools like artificial larynx and simple signal amplifiers. Moreover, to the best of authors' knowledge, companies involved in this field do not seem interested in implementing the current speech enhancement techniques to their products, for them to be applied to other domains. Some examples in this sense are Luminaud⁶, Griffin Laboratories⁷, and Atos Medical⁸. UltraVoice⁹ is another available device in the market which is still very invasive: *"There are three basic components which need to be located in the mouth and are specially mounted into an upper denture or an orthodontic retainer"*. Summarizing, in a first step HUM aims to reconstruct whispered speech of healthy speech apparatus, but we believe it's feasible to improve it in the future to cover esophageal speech too.

2.3 Speech enhancement and reconstruction techniques

Speech intelligibility is a topic of transversal interest for human activities. It plays a substantial role in digital audio forensics in perception of linguistic contexts in environmental and telephone interception. It also applies to countless areas, such as home automation (e.g., voice commands in human-computer interaction), public data and behavioral security (e.g., strengthening human action such as for emergency voice commands on aircraft), hardware and software applications for sung and spoken voice for artistic performances. Machine learning and signal processing research has enormously improved in recent years. However, scientific research has rarely turned into usable products for the speech in clinical contexts; this is probably due to the vastness of the topic and its wide possible application joined with the relative novelty of many techniques. Many signal-processing techniques demonstrate the possibility of enhancing speech intelligibility, but they need to be refined and strengthened to be used in everyday life. Nevertheless, none of the newly developed algorithms appear to be yet implemented in products for real-time usage. Real-time processing is extremely fundamental for concrete exploitation, but it requires experimentation in real contexts, well-defined speech databases, an interdisciplinary approach and first of all constant interfacing with end users.

Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) were successfully applied in tasks as Voice Conversion [29]. They lead to successful results also in Whisper-To-Speech tasks if combined with Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) as stated in [6]. In GMM architectures for Whisper-To-Speech tasks, pairs of NAM (Non-Audible-Murmur, speech recorded from the neck by means of a stethoscope microphone) and speech signals are fed to two GMM for spectral estimation and pitch estimation. In this case, the features and the power spectrum of both signals are

previously extracted [6], and the model tries to find the mapping between the source and target feature vectors. In the approach exploiting Hidden Markov Model (HMM) the source and target parameters are modeled by context-dependent phone-sized HMM. Then, an HMM recognition is applied on the input feature vectors and, lastly, a third HMM is used for the synthesis of the speech [34].

Seen the wide state of the art, at first, we decided to approach the challenge basing on machine learning techniques already mentioned in literature, but result was unsatisfactory from several points of view (Section 3). We therefore opted for a generative approach (section 4) which has been refined with mixed techniques coming to cross the original whispered speech with synthetic vowels to preserve the patient's timbre.

2.4 The added value of Digital Audio Forensics

Digital audio forensic techniques play a pivotal role in the exploitation of forensic noisy and degraded speech recordings for solving a wide range of questions. Therefore, it can be extremely helpful for face applied experimental research affected by a great amount of potential technical risks and subjective/objective variability, such as in clinical applications. These methodologies concern both the analysis of linguistic contents and the extraction of environmental and context noises, but most of the digital audio forensic applications are focused on human speech. For example, speaker's timbre characterization, speaker recognition, speaker profiling (age/gender/geographical origin), or characterization of pronunciation defects in relation to a linguistic norm [4], [22]. Moreover, forensic speech analysis has a strong interdisciplinary nature, combining different linguistic competences such as signal processing, audio coding and compression, digital restoration, psychoacoustics, perception, and linguistics (especially phonetics, phonology and sociophonetics). In forensics, both the segmental (vowels, consonants, silences, etc.) and the suprasegmental levels (the prosodic temporal behavior of local features such as intonation, amplitude envelope, etc.) and their mutual relationship are considered. Signal processing and features' extraction techniques are constantly improved, and, at the same time, the sociolinguistic and perceptive themes are considered, making the approach interesting for the clinical field too. Finally, compared to traditional linguistic and phonetic sciences, digital audio forensic techniques offer a different multidisciplinary and concrete approach.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

The architecture of the system in its last version is defined as follows. The work has been prototyped in Python and rewritten and optimized in C++ programming language in a second step. First, the microphone signal is acquired at chunks of 1024 samples, 44100Hz sample rate.

The choice of 44100Hz sample rate is crucial since allows us to further overlap-add these chunks into 5.6ms frames

⁶ <https://www.luminaud.com>

⁷ <http://www.griffinlab.com/catalog/>

⁸ <https://www.atosmedical.com>

⁹ <https://ultravoice.com/electrolarynx-speech-device-works/>

with still 256 samples: lower sample rates (e.g., 16kHz) don't give enough frame samples for our desired resolution.

Each chunk is then passed through a simple anti-Larsen filter to avoid audio feedback, to remove the need for ear-phones and allow the use through audio speakers. The anti-Larsen filter is a spectral filter that compares the mean of each magnitude band of the signal with its total magnitude spectrum; if the ratio of the power of a single band exceeds a threshold, a band-stop filter is set at the center frequency of the band, with a gain of -60dB, to suppress the feedback. Each chunk is further filtered with a first order high-pass filter (100Hz cutoff frequency) and then split into overlapping frames of 256 samples each with 50% overlap. The frames are windowed with two different methods:

- Bartlett window for audio signal processing.
- Hamming window for FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) and LPC (Linear Predictive Coding) analysis.

The windowed frames are then stored into stacks along with the previously computed frames, so that a 1024 samples chunk can always be reconstructed with inverse overlap-add technique. Each new frame is further analyzed: RMS is computed, and formant frequencies, bandwidths and amplitudes are calculated through LPC analysis.

Formants frequencies F1 and F2 are lowered by a fixed factor of 100Hz for F1 and 150Hz for F2, while F3 and F4 are left unaltered. Because of the instability of LPC with whispered speech, the resulting formant frequencies are rounded into the canonical approximation of frequency ranges of each formant [12], and these features are stacked into their respective data structures. The next step of the algorithm is to smooth the values of the features acquired with moving average filters, since there is too much variability in neighboring frame's features. F0 is then computed from the filtered RMS value in a similar way to the methodology described in [16] by adding to a fixed F0 value (chosen by the user) the result of the function $(\alpha * ((F2 - F1) + (F3 - F2)))$, with $\alpha = 0.008$.

If a frame is considered to contain whispered speech, a corresponding synthesized frame is generated according to the feature values of the frame. The synthesizer uses the technique of additive synthesis to generate up to 80 partials, and the volume of each is set according to the formants of the frame.

A filtered noise (4000Hz to 20000Hz) is then added to the sine mix to provide signal in the higher portion of the spectrum due to the later spectral multiplication, and the result is windowed with a Bartlett window. With corresponding whispered and synthesized, 3 overlapping frames (50% overlap) of 1024 samples are reconstructed with inverse overlap-add from the data stacks. This step is mandatory for the next processing because operating with 256 samples would generate too much variability in the resulting speech. The FFT is computed on the whispered frames, and two magnitude masks are calculated for each by averaging the magnitude spectrum with two different mean sizes, and then normalizing them. Each synthesized frame is transformed by FFT, each bin is multiplied by the two

corresponding bins of the previous masks, then it is translated back to the time domain by IFFT. The synthesized frames are finally windowed with a bartlett window, and the output frame is calculated by inverse overlap-add.

4. RESULTS AND FUTURE WORK

A preliminary evaluation has been performed on 20 naïve listeners to test the HUM's ability in increasing whisper intelligibility. They have been asked to transcribe the text of the male voice of the audio example (see link in the abstract) and rate the intelligibility and speech timbre's pleasantness on a 5 points scale as shown in Figure 2. The form online has been structured to be anonymous and GDPR compliant.

Figure 2: HUM's preliminary evaluation.

All the users correctly transcribed the audio, with average values for intelligibility and pleasantness equal to 4.05 and 2.45. We also asked to the same users to whisper using HUM to evaluate their user-experience and latency, which reach an average of 4 and 5 points: HUM results to be easy to use and perceived as essentially real-time. The more the spoken input is sighed and delicate, the clearer the reconstructed speech becomes: the speaker's effort is thus minimized. Consequently, the user experience encourages the speaker not to emit too much air and minimize the uttering effort. The aspect to be improved remains the timbre quality in terms of agreeableness and similarity with natural speech. In this sense, the intelligibility is perceptually linked to pleasantness, so that increasing the second we aim to improve the first too.

The future step will be collecting subjective perceptive assessments on a large scale in real contexts to move towards the commercial phase of the project. In order to base the evaluation on already tested methodologies, the state of the art was investigated regarding intelligibility and pleasantness of the reconstructed speech in different contexts [8], [14], [31], [32]. Several evaluation methodologies in the field of assistive technologies have been observed such as [18] or [20], but one that seems to be suitable to HUM regards music interaction [21]. Thus, we plan to base on the experience-focused evaluations described in [28] in order to take into account of the emotional aspects involving

user's voice but using open comments and over at least a month for each user.

Moreover, we plan to evaluate HUM on the most widely spoken non-tonal languages, and to start pilot studies on tonal languages also, to understand whether adaptation of the algorithm is necessary or not.

HUM has been injected in a miniaturized computer and a second design step began: it will be focused on the final design and construction of the tailor-made object. Some prerequisites have been collected during the first part of the project. They have been collected among 10 guests of the OTAF clinic in Lugano and personal contacts of the authors, suffering from different levels of paralysis affecting breathing and speech skills (one of them is quadriplegic). The modality consisted in direct discussion and open-ended questionnaires about their communication and technologies usability issues. Four of them followed each phase of the project guiding the user experience and the evaluation of partial results with direct comments and suggestions.

Thus, a series of obsolete technological choices or poorly conforming to the future wearability of VocalHUM have already been excluded tracing the boundaries within which to move for the choice of components. For example, regarding microphones, it will be necessary to place a lavalier microphone at the side of the mouth with wire connection. It will be supported by an ultralight customizable headband, which depending on the positions taken by the user can be replaced by a lateral single-ear support only. Regarding the micro-computer, the algorithm has been optimized and works on a Raspberry Pi4.

Future research developments on the algorithmic side will expand the possible users to laryngectomized speakers. Until a few years ago, due to the lack of technology, laryngophones and throat microphones [11] were only used to amplify the signal uttered by the patient [5], without considering the possibility to employ these sources to perform spectral analysis and reconstruction. Laryngophones and throat microphones were then successfully applied to voice activity detection and speaker recognition [24], [26] and, if combined with acoustic microphones, they were also used to partially reconstruct the speech spectrum [7], [25], [36], [37]. Despite extensive studies on this topic, the degraded speech produced by these patients is still very hard to understand. Although being psychologically important for users to have an acoustically acceptable voice, marketed tools are not so good from a qualitative and comfort point of view, at least not as much to reach a large-scale success among patients. Thus, users are still constrained to employ invasive devices, since hardware products are still limited to old-styled tools like artificial larynx and simple signal amplifiers, and, to the best of authors' knowledge, companies do not seem to be interested in implementing new solutions.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] Amano-Kusumoto, A., & Hosom, J. P. (2011). A review of research on speech intelligibility and correlations with acoustic features. Center for Spoken Language Understanding, Oregon Health and Science University (Technical Report CSLU-011-001).
- [2] Bradlow, A. R., Torretta, G. M., & Pisoni, D. B. (1996). Intelligibility of normal speech I: Global and fine-grained acoustic-phonetic talker characteristics. *Speech communication*, 20(3), 255.
- [3] Berkovitz, R. (1982). Digital equalization of audio signals. In *Audio Engineering Society Conference: 1st International Conference: Digital Audio*. Audio Engineering Society.
- [4] Broeders, T. (2001, July). Forensic speech and audio analysis Forensic Linguistics 1998-2001. In *Proceedings 13th INTERPOL Forensic Science Symposium, Lyon, France D* (Vol. 2, pp. 54-84).
- [5] Cohen, A., Van den Broecke, M. P., & Van Geel, R. C. (1984). A Study of Pitch Phenomena and Applications in Electrolarynx Speech. In *Speech and Language* (Vol. 11, pp. 197-248). Elsevier.
- [6] Doi, H., Nakamura, K., Toda, T., Saruwatari, H., & Shikano, K. (2010). Esophageal speech enhancement based on statistical voice conversion with Gaussian mixture models. *IEICE TRANSACTIONS on Information and Systems*, 93(9), 2472-2482.
- [7] Erzin, E. (2009). Improving throat microphone speech recognition by joint analysis of throat and acoustic microphone recordings. *IEEE transactions on audio, speech, and language processing*, 17(7), 1316-1324.
- [8] Finizia, C., Lindström, J., & Dotevall, H. (1998). Intelligibility and perceptual ratings after treatment for laryngeal cancer: laryngectomy versus radiotherapy. *The Laryngoscope*, 108(1), 138-143.
- [9] French, N. R., & Steinberg, J. C. (1947). Factors governing the intelligibility of speech sounds. *The journal of the Acoustical society of America*, 19(1), 90-119.
- [10] Gao, M. (2003). Tones in whispered Chinese: Articulatory features and perceptual cues.
- [11] Hanjun Liua & Manwa L. Ng. Electrolarynx in voice rehabilitation. *Auris Nasus Larynx* 34 (2007) 327-332.
- [12] Kent, R. D., & Vorperian, H. K. (2018). Static measurements of vowel formant frequencies and bandwidths: A review. *Journal of communication disorders*, 74, 74-97.
- [13] Jovičić, S. T. (1998). Formant feature differences between whispered and voiced sustained vowels. *Acta Acustica united with Acustica*, 84(4), 739-743.
- [14] Lagerberg, T. B., Åsberg, J., Hartelius, L., & Persson, C. (2014). Assessment of intelligibility

using children's spontaneous speech: Methodological aspects. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders*, 49(2), 228-239.

- [15] Lim, B. P. (2011). *Computational differences between whispered and non-whispered speech*. University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign.
- [16] Loizou, P. C., & Kim, G. (2010). Reasons why current speech-enhancement algorithms do not improve speech intelligibility and suggested solutions. *IEEE transactions on audio, speech, and language processing*, 19(1), 47-56.
- [17] Morris, R. W., & Clements, M. A. (2002). Reconstruction of speech from whispers. *Medical Engineering & Physics*, 24(7-8), 515-520.
- [18] Onitilo, A. A., Shour, A. R., Puthoff, D. S., Tanimu, Y., Joseph, A., & Sheehan, M. T. (2023). Evaluating the adoption of voice recognition technology for real-time dictation in a rural healthcare system: A retrospective analysis of dragon medical one. *Plos one*, 18(3), e0272545.
- [19] Rayner, P., Godsill, S., & Cappé, O. (2002). Digital audio restoration. In *Applications of digital signal processing to audio and acoustics* (pp. 133-194). Springer, Boston, MA.
- [20] Reichle, J. (2011). Evaluating assistive technology in the education of persons with severe disabilities. *Journal of Behavioral Education*, 20, 77-85.
- [21] Reimer, P. C., & Wanderley, M. M. (2021, April). Embracing Less Common Evaluation Strategies for Studying User Experience in NIME. In *NIME 2021*. PubPub.
- [22] Riekhakaynen, E. I. (2020, January). Corpora of Russian spontaneous speech as a tool for modelling natural speech production and recognition. In *2020 10th Annual Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC)* (pp. 0406-0411). IEEE.
- [23] Robinson, T., Hochberg, M., & Renals, S. (1994, April). IPA: Improved phone modelling with recurrent neural networks. In *Proceedings of ICASSP'94. IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing* (Vol. 1, pp. I-37). IEEE.
- [24] Sahidullah, M., Gonzalez Hautamäki, R., Lehmann, T. D. A., Kinnunen, T., Tan, Z. H., Hautamäki, V., ... & Pitkänen, M. (2016). Robust speaker recognition with combined use of acoustic and throat microphone speech.
- [25] Shahina, A., & Yegnanarayana, B. (2007). Mapping speech spectra from throat microphone to close-speaking microphone: A neural network approach. *EURASIP Journal on Advances in Signal Processing*, 2007, 1-10.
- [26] Sahidullah, M., Thomsen, D. A. L., Hautamäki, R. G., Kinnunen, T., Tan, Z. H., Parts, R., & Pitkänen, M. (2017). Robust voice liveness detection and speaker verification using throat microphones. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 26(1), 44-56.
- [27] Sharifzadeh, H. R., McLoughlin, I. V., & Russell, M. J. (2010). Toward a comprehensive vowel space for whispered speech. In *2010 7th International Symposium on Chinese Spoken Language Processing* (pp. 65-68). IEEE.
- [28] Springett, M. (2009). Evaluating cause and effect in user experience. *Digital Creativity*, 20(3), 197-204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14626260903083637>
- [29] Stylianou, Y. (1996). Harmonic plus noise models for speech, combined with statistical methods, for speech and speaker modification. *Ph. D thesis, Ecole Nationale Supérieure des Telecommunications*.
- [30] Strassel, S., Miller, D., Walker, K., & Cieri, C. (2003). Shared resources for robust speech-to-text technology. In *Eighth European Conference on Speech Communication and Technology*.
- [31] Van Nuffelen, G., Middag, C., De Bodt, M., & Martens, J. P. (2009). Speech technology-based assessment of phoneme intelligibility in dysarthria. *International journal of language & communication disorders*, 44(5), 716-730.
- [32] Walshe, M., Miller, N., Leahy, M., & Murray, A. (2008). Intelligibility of dysarthric speech: perceptions of speakers and listeners. *International journal of language & communication disorders*, 43(6), 633-648.
- [33] Weitzman, R. S., Sawashima, M., Hirose, H., & Ushijima, T. (1976). Devoiced and whispered vowels in Japanese. *Annual Bulletin, Research Institute of Logopedics and Phoniatrics*, 10(61-79), 29-31.
- [34] Tran, V. A., Bailly, G., Loevenbruck, H., & Toda, T. (2009, September). Multimodal HMM-based NAM-to-speech conversion. In *Interspeech 2009-10th Annual Conference of the International Speech Communication Association* (pp. 656-659).
- [35] Tsunoda, K., Ohta, Y., Niimi, S., Soda, Y., & Hirose, H. (1997). Laryngeal adjustment in whispering: magnetic resonance imaging study. *Annals of Otolaryngology & Rhinology & Laryngology*, 106(1), 41-43.
- [36] Turan, M. A. T. (2018). Enhancement of Throat Microphone Recordings Using Gaussian Mixture Model Probabilistic Estimator. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1804.05937*.

- [37] Zheng, Y., Liu, Z., Zhang, Z., Sinclair, M., Droppo, J., Deng, L., ... & Huang, X. (2003, November). Air- and bone-conductive integrated microphones for robust speech detection and enhancement. In *2003 IEEE Workshop on Automatic Speech Recognition and Understanding (IEEE Cat. No. 03EX721)* (pp. 249-254). IEEE.